

Soil micronutrients and their functions

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Abstract

Most of the nutrients required for plant growth come from the soil. But to some extent, this nutrient requirement of crops can be met by chemical fertilizers, green manures, manures, compost, crop rotation, inclusion of leguminous crops etc. It is necessary to have scientific information about the quantity, form, availability of major nutrients in the soil and also the method, quantity, etc. of chemical fertilizers. A total of 17 different nutrients are required for proper growth of crops. An element is essential if a plant cannot complete its life cycle without it, if no other element can perform the same function, and if it is directly involved in nutrition. An essential nutrient required by the plant in large amounts is called a macronutrient, while one required in very small amounts is termed a micronutrient. Missing or inadequate supplies of nutrients adversely affect plant growth, leading to stunted growth, slow growth, chlorosis, or cell death. About half the essential nutrients are micronutrients such as boron, chlorine, manganese, iron, zinc, copper, molybdenum, nickel, silicon, and sodium. These nutrients are secondary nutrients and called as micronutrients. The present research topic gathers several studies that focus on the beneficial role of micronutrients in plant nutrition, while aiming at the same time to set the borderlines between excessive use and deficiencies in plant development.

Keyword: *Micronutrients, Roles, Deficiencies and Management.*

Introduction

Plants require only light, water, and about 17 elements to support all their biochemical needs. These 17 elements are called essential nutrients. For an element to be regarded as essential, three criteria are required: A plant cannot complete its life cycle without the element, no other element can perform the function of the element, and the element is directly involved in plant nutrition. The essential elements can be divided into macronutrients and micronutrients. Nutrients that plants require in larger amounts are called macronutrients. About half of the essential elements are considered macronutrients: carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium, and sulfur. The first of these macronutrients, carbon (C), is required to form carbohydrates, proteins, nucleic acids, and many other compounds; it is, therefore, present in all macromolecules. On average, the dry weight (excluding water) of a cell is 50 percent carbon, making it a key part of plant biomolecules. In addition to macronutrients, organisms require various elements in small amounts. These micronutrients, or trace elements, are present in very small quantities. The seven main micronutrients include boron, chlorine, manganese, iron, zinc, copper, and molybdenum. Boron (B) is believed to be involved in carbohydrate transport in plants; it also assists in metabolic regulation. Boron deficiency will often result in bud dieback. Chlorine (Cl) is necessary for osmosis and ionic balance; it also plays a role in photosynthesis. Copper (Cu) is a component of some enzymes. Symptoms of copper deficiency include browning of leaf tips and chlorosis (yellowing of the leaves). Iron (Fe) is essential for chlorophyll synthesis, which is why an iron deficiency results in chlorosis. Manganese (Mn) activates some important enzymes involved in chlorophyll formation. Manganese-deficient plants will develop chlorosis between the veins of its leaves. The availability of manganese is partially dependent on soil

pH. Molybdenum (Mo) is essential to plant health as it is used by plants to reduce nitrates into usable forms. Some plants use it for nitrogen fixation; thus, it may need to be added to some soils before seeding legumes. Zinc (Zn) participates in chlorophyll formation and also activates many enzymes. Symptoms of zinc deficiency include chlorosis and stunted growth. Deficiencies in any of these nutrients, particularly the macronutrients and micronutrients, can adversely affect plant growth. Depending on the specific nutrient, a lack can cause stunted growth, slow growth, or chlorosis. Extreme deficiencies may result in leaves showing signs of cell death. Let's learn a little more about these micronutrients functions, deficiency symptoms and management.

1. Iron (Fe):-

Functions of iron nutrients:-

1. This nutrient helps plants produce green matter.
2. With an adequate supply of iron, crops can absorb other nutrients in abundance.
3. Iron is a modulator of many hormones.
4. 100 to 500 milligrams per kilogram of iron is considered a suitable nutrient in plants.

Symptoms of Iron Deficiency (Shown in Fig. 1):-

1. Iron deficiency first appears on young leaves.
2. A major symptom is yellowing of leaf veins but veins remaining green.
3. In case of iron deficiency, leaves do not turn green. Leaves become hollow, new branches become crooked.
4. Soils with more than 5 percent free limestone are deficient in iron.
5. If the deficiency is severe, the entire veins also turn yellow and the entire leaves turn pale yellow and white and fall off.
6. The crop does not flower regularly. Fruits are smaller in size.
7. If you touch the leaf, it feels like paper.

Fertilizers containing iron:-

1. Iron: Iron sulphate : 19 percent : 10 to 25 kg/ha.
2. Iron : Ferrous ammonium sulphate : 14 percent : 10 to 25 kg/ha.
3. Iron : Ferrous EDTA chelate : 12 percent : 10 to 25 kg/ha.

Management :-

Fertilizers containing iron should be used as recommended according to the type of land and crops. Generally, 20 kg/ha of ferric fertilizer should be applied along with organic fertilizers or 1 per cent (100g in 10 liters of water) iron sulphate or ferrous ammonium sulphate by spraying at sensitive stages of crop growth.

2. Manganese (Mn)

Function :-

1. Helping in the process of photosynthesis.
2. Producing vitamins like carotene, riboflavin, ascorbic acid.
3. Affects the rate of absorption of calcium and potassium.

Symptoms of Manganese Deficiency (Shown in Fig. 1) :-

1. The veins of the new leaves remain green and the interveins turn yellow.
2. Yellow spots appear on the yellowed area and the leaf looks webbed.
3. Black and oily spots appear on the leaves.
4. The process of photosynthesis is hindered.

Manganese Fertilizers :-

1. Manganese Sulphate : 30 percent : 10 to 25 kg/ha
2. Manganese oxide
3. Chelated Manganese : 12 percent : 10 to 25 kg/ha

Management:

Manganese fertilizers should be used as recommended according to the soil and type of crops. In general, 20 kg/ha of manganese fertilizer should be applied along with organic fertilizers or by spraying 0.5 percent (50g in 10L of water) manganese sulfate at sensitive stages of crop growth.

3. Zinc(Zn)-

Functions of Zinc in Crops :-

1. The essential nutrient in the formation of oxygen mainly assists in the formation of indole acetic acid, which helps in vigorous growth of the crop.
2. Zinc is essential for starch formation and root growth in crops.
3. Zinc affects seed and stem ripening.
4. Zinc is essential in the production of green algae and carbohydrates.
5. The presence of adequate amount of zinc in the plant cells helps the plant survive even at low temperatures.

Zinc Deficiency Symptoms (Shown in Fig. 1):-

1. Zinc deficiency causes the leaves to become small, narrow and tapering.
2. The growth of the pods is limited and the leaves turn into clumps.
3. The leaf lacks green fluid. The veins of older leaves turn yellow.
4. Sugar accumulates on the surface of the leaves.
5. The tree has few flowers.

6. Crop flowering and fruit ripening are delayed.

Zinc Fertilizers:-

1. Zinc Sulphate : 21 percent : 20 to 40 kg/ha
2. Zinc ethoxylate : 12 percent : 20 to 40 kg/ha

Remedy:

Zinc fertilizers should be used as recommended according to the type of land and crops. In general, 20 kg/ha of zinc fertilizer should be applied along with organic fertilizers or 0.5 per cent (50 g in 10 L of water) zinc sulphate by spraying at sensitive stages of crop growth.

4. Copper (Cu)-

Functions of copper nutrients :-

1. Inducers activated in essential processes of crop growth.
2. To promote the reproductive process in the plant.
3. Helping to produce vitamin A.
4. Involvement in fruit ripening process.

Copper Deficiency Symptoms (Shown in Fig. 1):-

1. Copper deficiency is found in leaves.
2. First the young leaves turn dark green and then turn pale yellow and fall off.
3. Leaves bend near the stem. The leaves turn yellow and fold and curl.
4. Trunks get crazy crooked. As soon as the flowers do not bloom, the flower dies.
5. The prevalence of fungal diseases increases.
6. We call it dieback when it dries down from the branches.

Copper Fertilizers :-

1. Copper sulphate : 25 percent : 5 to 10 kg/ha
2. Copper EDTA Chelated: 12 percent : 5 to 10 kg/ha

Management :-

Copper fertilizers should be used as recommended according to the type of land and crops. In general, 10 kg/ha of copper-containing fertilizer should be applied along with organic fertilizers or 0.5 percent (50 g in 10 L of water) copper sulfate by spraying at sensitive stages of crop growth.

5. Boron (B) :-

Functions :-

1. Boron balances sugars and starches in crops.
2. It is essential in the transport of sugars and carbohydrates in the crop.
3. It is essential in pollination and seed production.
4. It is essential for regular cell wall formation.
5. It is essential for regular cell division, nitrogen metabolism and protein metabolism.
6. It is essential in crop water management.

Boron Deficiency Symptoms (Shown in Fig. 1):-

1. Boron deficiency causes rotting of young roots and shoots.
2. The new stem dies mainly by wilting.
3. The branches formed are short length.
4. The leaves turn yellow and become thick, coarse and hard. The shape of the leaves becomes irregular.
5. Cracks on the trunk make it brittle.
6. Fruits are blighted before maturity.
7. Fruits grow into curved shapes. A black spot occurs on the fruit and in the fruit.

Boron Fertilizers :-

1. Boron: 11 percent : 5 to 10 kg/ha
2. Boron : Solubor : 20 percent : 5 to 10 kg/ha

Solution :-

1. Fertilizers containing boron should be used as recommended according to the type of soil and crops.
2. Borax / Solubor should be applied during sensitive stages of crop growth.

6. Molybdenum (Mo) :-

Functions :-

1. Molybdenum acts in the conversion of nitrates into amino acids in the plant.
2. Essential in symbiotic nitrogen stabilization.

Solution :-

Molybdenum fertilizers should be used as recommended by soil and crop type.

3. Aiding in phosphate formation and vitamin K formation.

Symptoms of molybdenum deficiency (Shown in Fig. 1):-

1. Mainly found on the old leaves near the bottom and adjacent leaves above them.
2. The leaves turn yellow and brown spots appear on them and the leaves become discolored.
3. The edges of the leaves are curled and the leaves die.
4. The tree flowers very little.

Molybdenum Fertilizers :-

1. Sodium molybdenum : 39 percent : 50 to 100 g/ha
2. Ammonium molybdenum : 52 percent : 50 to 100 g/ha

Fig.1 Different micronutrients deficiency symptoms

Conclusion-

This study has been carried out to investigate the roles, deficiency symptoms and management practices of micronutrients in plants, as deficiencies of any of these micronutrients, can adversely affect plant growth as well as production of the crop. The successful management of such micronutrients in soil will promote nutrients efficacy and market acceptability of the various control measures.

Reference

1. Katyal, J. C. and Agarwal, S. C. 1982. Micronutrient research in India. *Fert. News* 27(2):66-86.
2. Khan, M. A., Castro-Guerrero, N., and Mendoza-Cozatl, D. G. (2014). Moving toward a precise nutrition: preferential loading of seeds with essential nutrients over non-essential toxic elements. *Front. Plant Sci.* 5:51.
3. Marschner, H. (1995) *Mineral Nutrition of Higher Plants*. Academic Press, Orlando, Florida, USA.

4. Rajeev-Kumar, Singh, K. P. and Sarkar, A. K. (1993) cumulative effects of cropping and fertilizer use on the status of micronutrients in soil and crop. *Fertilizer News*, 38 (11), 13-17.
5. Schmidt W, Thomine S and Buckhout TJ (2020) Editorial: Iron Nutrition and Interactions in Plants. *Front. Plant Sci.* 10:1670
6. Sperotto RA, Ricachenevsky FK, Williams LE, Vasconcelos MW and Menguer PK (2014) from soil to seed: micronutrient movement into and within the plant. *Front. Plant Sci.* 5:438
7. Takkar, P. N. (1996) Micronutrient research and sustainable agricultural productivity in India. *Journal of the Indian Society of Soil Science*, 44, 562-581.
8. Thapa, S., Bhandari, A., Ghimire, R., Xue, Q., and Kidwaro, F. (2021). Managing Micronutrients for improving soil fertility, health and soybean yield. *J. Sustainability*